

Recommendation 14:

Using 'Crowdsourcing' to meet the public sector need 'Civil servants as a community of change'

Actual solutions and services:

Currently, crowdsourcing applied in the public sector refers to obtaining needed services, ideas, or content by soliciting contributions from a large group of people, especially an online community, rather than from employees or suppliers. To meet the need 'Civil servants as a community of change', crowdsourcing is to be applied **within** the public sector. This means government setting up a microtasking platform, not just for citizen engagement, but as a way to harness the knowledge and skills of its own workers across multiple departments and agencies.

SWOT Analysis	
Strengths <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access to new pools of external talent and expertise from a diversity of fields • Reduced cost of conducting research and development • Less cost compared to outsourcing • Incorporation of end users/customers early in the development process • Faster design and prototyping • Potential for higher quality • Increased agility and faster time to market 	Weaknesses <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruiting and retaining users can be a challenge • Types of users' contributions are mostly limited (e.g. review/rate/tag/etc.) • Difficulty in combining and evaluating user contributions - unstructured information gathered, cumbersome to filter • Good quality of user contributions is not guaranteed • Difficulty in keeping hold of confidential information and intellectual property
Opportunities <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collective Intelligence • Co-creation and collaboration for needs tackling 	Threats <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical concerns • Private Data Exposure • IPR issues

Civil servants as a community of change:

It is widely recognized that people, not organisations, drive innovation. This is even more true in the realm of public sector. Thus, it is necessary that the responsibility and the will to drive changes percolates down the hierarchy and become a responsibility at all levels: from top-level management to midlevel managers and front line staff. They must increase their ability to drive change by collaborating more and differently with each other and with end-users such as citizens, businesses and the third sector. Public sector innovation activities must become more embedded structurally, more strategic and more systematic. Sub needs include the need for a flexible public sector and the reflection that authorities need to be more open-minded. To further illustrate through the informants' voices: "Need of an organizational structure that is flexible and adaptable" and "The collaboration between different municipalities is still difficult".

Crowdsourcing:

*Describes the processes for sourcing a task or challenge to a broad, distributed set of contributors using the web and social collaboration techniques. Each person's contribution combines with those of others to achieve a cumulative result. Crowdsourcing applications typically include mechanisms to attract the desired participants, stimulate relevant contributions and select winning ideas or solutions.**

* Gartner IT Glossary – Crowdsourcing, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/crowdsourcing/>